

Study of an Effectiveness of Swachh Bharat Mission of the Government of India in Malasa, Kanpur DEHAT

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Abstract:- Sanitation is the need for all and to speed up this work, to accomplish widespread sanitation and to put the excellent spotlight on the sanitation the Prime Minister of India sent off the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan on October second, 2014, and it was a fitting recognition for the 150th birthday celebration of Mahatma Gandhi. Its goal is to make the country liberated from open defecation framework, acquire an uncommon change individuals' way of behaving and telling them that why sanitisation is much significant in once life. Following the Prime Minister's clarion for every person to commit no less than 100 hours of Swachhata all through the year in the program Swachh Bharat Summer Internship. The point of the program is to bring youth the nation over, a potential chance to make critical commitment to the Swachhata upheaval, coordinating them in friendly administrations and advancement of their abilities. Making mindfulness, assemble foundation and casing regulations are the normal disinfection drives sent off by the public authority worldwide. Enlivened by the Prime Minister, individuals around the country followed and taken the stride to contribute and figures out the worth of tidiness. Not many of the populace don't know about the Abhiyan because of absence of sources in Malasa, Kanpur Dehat. There could be no appropriate channelization of assets in country regions for development of latrines and act of spontaneity of sanitation offices. Defilement being wild in workplaces likewise have difficulties to the mission. Individuals are having old propensity for defecating out in fields as it's been said monetary emergency is the serious issue with them. The strategies being utilized by the scientists are house to house correspondence, nukkad nataks, banner making, film screening, and so on for spurring them to involve latrines and keep up with the neatness in the climate in the town Malasa which contains 3,605 individuals out of which 371 families are the BPL Card clients. The review uncovers that individuals are having uplifting perspective towards the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan.

Keywords:- Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, Summer Internship, Open Defecation System, Sanitation, Swachhata Revolution.

I. INTRODUCTION

No innovation in the past two hundred years has done more to save lives and improve health than the sanitation revolution triggered by invention of the toilets. But it did not go far enough. It only reached one-third of the world.

-Sylvia Mathews Burwell

The need that has an impact on everyone's life is sanitation. On October 2, 2014, Indian Prime Minister Shri. Narendra Modi established the Swachh Bharat Mission to intensify efforts, achieve universal sanitation coverage, and centre attention on sanitation. The Swachh Bharat Mission (Grameen) and the Swachh Bharat Mission are the two submissions that the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation (MDWS) secretary will use to coordinate the mission (urban).

As a suitable homage to Mahatma Gandhi's 150th birthday, Swachh Bharat Abhiyaan seeks to achieve Swachh Bharat by 2019 by building 90 million toilets in rural India at a project cost of Rs. 1.96 lakh crore. More than 35% of the world's population, or an estimated 2.5 billion people, lack access to even the most basic sanitation. The notion is that improving access to water and sanitation will go more smoothly in nations with greater GDPs. India had 525 million or more people practise open defecation in 2017, making it the nation with the biggest number of such persons.

The estimated cost of Swachh Bharat Abhiyaan is more than Rs. 620 billion (\$ 9.0 billion). The government offers incentives in the amount of Rs. 12000 for every toilet built by a BPL family.

The nationwide sanitation coverage increased to 65% in 2017 from 38.7% in October 2014, before the campaign's launch.

By the 15th of February 2018, the 11th stage, 314 districts, and 3.25 lakh villages had all been proclaimed free of open defecation. The goal of Swachh Bharat Abhiyaan is to end open defecation by building toilets that are owned by both households and communities.

Fig 1:- A Government appointed painter writing awareness message on village wall

➤ *Swachh Bharat Mission Promotion*

“Mann Ki Baat”, Prime Minister Narendra Modi frequently discuss the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan on the national radio channel, through which he spreads awareness among the population.

“Through Brand Ambassadors”, the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan has been endorsed by many of the well-known faces- Amitabh Bacchan, Anushka Sharma, Virat Kohli, Sachin Tendulkar, etc.

➤ *Promotion And Execution*

“Swachh Bharat Summer Internship”, the internship was organized by 3 ministries, HRD, Sports and Sanitation. Objective is to engage the youth and develop the skill towards sanitation.

➤ *SWACHH BHARAT SUMMER INTERNSHIP – 100 Hours of Swachhata*

Following the Prime Minister’s clarion call on 2nd October 2014 for each individual to devote at least 100 hours of Swachhata through the year. The aim of the program is to bring youth across the country, an opportunity to make significant contribution to the Swachhata revolution, integration them in community service and to develop their skills. In SWACHH BHARAT SUMMER INTERNSHIP 50,314 Swachh Bharat pledges has been taken, 11,121 Swachh Bharat challenges taken, 26,564 Swachh Bharat activities have been done, 37,685 are the active participation of the youth, 1,310,075 hours have been contributed and 4,405 Swachh Bharat pakhwada activities have been done.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Swachh Bharat Abhiyan or Clean India Mission is a campaign in India that aims to clean the streets, roads and infrastructure in cities, towns and rural areas of India. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan was launched by the Government of India on 2 October 2014 as a tribute to Mahatma Gandhi on his 150th birthday. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan's goals include eliminating open defecation through the construction of community and household owned latrines and the establishment of a responsible mechanism for monitoring toilet usage. . Abhiyan is government run and mission aims to achieve Open Defecation Free (ODF) Project by 2nd October 2019, by

building 90 million toilets in rural India at cost Rs 1.96 lakh crore (\$30 billion) project. The mission also contributes to the achievement of sustainable development goals. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan was officially launched by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in Rajghat, New Delhi. In 2015, 965 million people worldwide were forced to practice open defecation (OD). The consequences of open defecation are many, such as acute intestinal infections, diarrhoea due to poor water supply, adverse pregnancy outcomes, and life-threatening violence against women and girls. . Chronic effects include soil-transmitted helminth infections, anaemia, giardiasis, environmental enteropathy, and more. Open defecation is a global health problem. Open defecation and wastewater contamination in drinking water are a common problem in India. In 2017, India was the country with the largest number of open defecations, about 525 million people. Sanitation is an investment with high economic returns. Lack of sanitation is a major public health problem in India. Poor sanitation has been shown to be a major cause of intestinal infections in young children. One-third of the world's 2.5 billion people without access to improved sanitation live in India, as do two-thirds of the 1.1 billion people who defecate in the open and 1/ 4 out of 1.5 million people die each year from diarrheal diseases. Most people in rural areas are not aware of the link between cleanliness and health. In most villages, defecation is the “way of life”. This practice is the most dangerous health and environmental problem. The mission consists of two submissions: Swachh Bharat Abhiyan “Gramin” under the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation; and Swachh Bharat Abhiyan "Urban", under the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs. In Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (Gramin), 38.7% of rural households have private latrines as of October 2, 2014, the date Swachh Bharat Abhiyan was introduced. 249,811 defecation-free villages in 2017, of which 157,935 (63%) were officially verified and 207 districts did not defecate as of 2017. Where there was no feces and each household and public facility /communities use safe technology to dispose of manure in a way that is free from surface soil, ground or surface water contamination, flies and inaccessible animals, and no human handling of fresh manure, then This village is said to be defecation free (ODF). In Swachh Bharat Abhiyan (municipality), as of September 29, 2017, 44,650 wards have collected 100% door-to-door waste, 12,526 community toilets built in three years, and 11,806 public toilets plus is built. In India, about 117,000

children under the age of 5 die each year from diarrhoea caused by poor sanitation. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is expected to cost 620 billion rupees (\$9.0 billion). The Government of India encourages Rs 12,000 for each toilet built by a family below the poverty line (BPL).

Prime Minister Narendra Modi selected different public figures for the campaign such as: Shilpa Shetty, Sachin Tendulkar, Priyanka Chopra, Amitabh Bacchan, Akshay Kumar, Vidya Balan, Shah Rukh Khan, Shashi Tharoor, Baba Ramdev, Virat Kohli, Mahendra Singh Dhoni, Anushka Sharma and Vice President of India M.V. Naidu. In 2017, the national sanitation coverage rate increased from 38.7% to 65%. this figure was 90% in 2018. 11 states, 314 districts and 3,25 lakh villages were declared to ban defecation on 15 February 2018. Swachh Bharat Abhiyan aims to improve sanitation facilities. birth, eliminate open defecation in India, to convert unhygienic toilets into toilet flushing, eliminate manual flushing and raise awareness of healthy practices. And after the Prime Minister stated, 7,98,01,056 household toilets have been built since October 2, 2014, 4,09,442 villages without open defecation, 421 districts without defecation, 19 Union states/territories do not have open defecation.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study comprising of research work in which we have used Probability Sampling Technique, in which Stratified Sampling Technique has been used. Total 241 people response have been taken into consideration, their views for the structured questionnaire prepared on the topic. Further we have segregated the population who are truly important for this research work for the “study of an effectiveness of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan in the village Malasa”. Total 186 people have been taken into consideration after the questionnaire and unstructured interview. Their collective views have been compiled and have been discussed. The methods which have also been used by the researchers are: - Door to Door communication, questionnaire, student awareness program, nukkad natak and personal interview.

IV. ANALYSIS (GROUND REALITIES)

Gandhiji once said, “So long as you do not take the broom and the bucket in your hands, you cannot make your towns and cities clean.” Inspired by these lines people around the Nation followed and taken the footstep and understands the value in sake of cleanliness. The objective of the Abhiyan is to promote public cleanliness and sanitation and transform India into a Clean India. The Swachh Bharat Abhiyan has been well supported by the people from different section of the society. But when we talk about the reality, it is found that people are not getting the proper support and information for the implementation of the task of building the toilets. As an example, “A poverty-stricken woman in Bihar's Gaya district sold her cow to construct a toilet at her house, in her late 60s,

sold the cow which was the only source of livelihood for her family”.

The study, released by the National Institute of Nutrition (NIN) on 26 September 2017 found that:

- 32-33 percent of scheduled caste/tribe boys under five years of age are underweight, compared to 21 percent in the general population.
- 36 percent of boys under five years of age with illiterate fathers were underweight, compared to 16 percent with college-educated fathers.
- 50.2 percent boys, 44.6 percent of girls with no access to toilets are stunted, compared to 26 percent boys and 24 percent girls who live in homes with toilets.

Offenders from a higher socio-economic class retaliate violently simply because the advice is given from someone lower on the social strata. An e-rickshaw driver in Delhi, perhaps inspired by Prime Minister Narendra Modi's Swachh Bharat initiative, objected to two young men urinating in the open. He requested that they use a public toilet. They responded by returning with a dozen others and bludgeoning him to death. Are these really the educated people we are living with! The real issue is that we don't take advice, no matter how well-meaning or unless it comes from an authority figure. The awareness of Swachh Bharat is growing, which is commendable. However, what is sorely lacking is infrastructure and laws. Government, around the world, do three things in common when launching sanitation drives: Create awareness, build infrastructure, and frame laws.

➤ Reality of Malasa

Malasa village, covering the area of 758.4 hectare, with population of about 3,605 people and 599 households out of which 371 families are the BPL Card (below poverty line) users. The people living in Malasa (few) are aware of the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan and have built their own toilets under the Rs. 12,000 schemes. People their wants to build their own toilets but lacks money and information.

They have built the pits, but still the complete construction is left as one the villager has said in Hindi (verbatim), “वो लोग आए थे, फोटो लेकर चले गए, अब जब पैसा आयेगा तो आगे का काम कराएंगे, क्ोकं क हमारे पास तो है नही”.

Malasa is a village with no public toilets, and the toilets which they use are not in proper condition. When it comes to cleanliness, the village lacks DUSTBIN, there's not even a single dustbin in the village to dump the household garbage, daily household garbage is dumped into the sole pond of the village and the rest is dumped in front of the houses or on the road. About 40% of the villagers are not aware of the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan due to lack of medium and sources. Financial status of the village is very poor. According to them, construction of toilets cost more than Rs.12, 000, they are not able to afford their daily expenses then how will they manage to build toilets by their own.

Fig 2. Semiconstructed pits.

Fig 3. Fully constructed toilet

➤ Challenges

India has a very old habit of defecation outside their houses. Despite having sufficient money to build toilets, people, especially in rural areas go outside for excretion.

There are still no proper dumping facilities on highways due to which people throw their waste on roads carelessly. There is no proper channelization of funds in rural areas for construction of toilets and improvisation of sanitation

➤ Challenges In Malasa

Fig 4. Dumping of garbage in a trolley

Fig 5. Pond where most of the garbage is dumped

Fig. 4 and fig. 5 above shows how the garbage is ill-treated in the village.

People are having old habit of defecating out in fields. They are not aware of importance of sanitation in one's life.

They have to face different kinds of problems like: -

Difficulties faced by girls out there, the distance they have to travel is very long sometimes, hospital is 5kms away from the village, financial crisis is a major problem there, people are having no space for building of toilets, they are not habitual of using toilets, availing water is not an easy task for them.

➤ General Perception

Study found that people felt that Swachh Bharat Abhiyan is a useful programme for the community. Pradhan stated that Swachh Bharat Abhiyan helps in the development of the country and also agreed that it has brought changes on the ground level. These findings reflect the positive perception of the community towards Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. Current study revealed that all the people must actively participate in cleanliness and sanitation activities.

facilities. The officials responsible for the construction of toilets in villages scoff at people (especially females) and harass them which is quite immoral in its sense.

Corruption, being rampant in offices, also poses challenges to the mission. People in need don't get enough funds by the government and they have to add their money to build a suitable toilet.

Most of the literate people think that being a part of Swachhata Abhiyan and initiating is huge opportunity for the society. This could be, because people are having better understanding now and are aware of environmental hygiene. Majority of the people thinks that this Swachhata Abhiyan has been started for the political benefit only.

➤ Perception of Malasa People

People of Malasa, Kanpur Dehat have an incredibly positive perception regarding the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan initiated by Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi. People there are actively participating in the activities regarding cleanliness. According to them the government is doing very well in this field. The schemes which are now a day's introduced are in their welfare and they are very happily and actively participating. They do believe in the government and are ready to coordinate with them. They believe that Swachh Bharat Abhiyan invites women safety and is very useful and beneficial. But as a coin has two faces, similarly their perceptions are also different. According to few of them this

is a waste of time and money. They believe that government is doing this for their own benefits so that they can earn more. People there are saying that no one comes to see how you are managing your day-to-day life and sacrifices you do to survive. They believe that all these things are fake. And is not done in villager's welfare.

V. DISCUSSION

85% of the 3,605 people are aware of the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. They get to know this from various sources like from advertisements, Modi Ji's Mann ki baat, from the panchayat, from other people and few of them get to know this from the interns i.e., by us. About 75% people are having their own toilets and these toilets are regularly used by them too. But it has come out from the study that there are few people who have their own toilets, but they prefer open defecation more. The reason behind this is that, that they feel like a behavioural change in daily normal life, the second reason is "how a daughter-in-law can to the same toilet which has been used by the father-in-law. About 20% of the remaining 25% people regularly go to the same place for defecation. The reason behind not constructing their own toilets is: -

- They are not aware of the importance of using toilets.
- They are having no space for building them.
- They are going through financial crisis.
- They think that this against their nature.
- They take it as a behavioural change.

Problems faced by them while practising open defecation:

- Sanitation and hygiene.
- Disease.
- Mosquitoes and insects.
- Distance from their house.
- Water arrangement problems.
- Problems faced during rainy seasons.
- Difficulties faced by women.

People are aware that Swachh Bharat Abhiyan invites women safety. The schools and college of the village are consisting of separate toilets for girls in the building, but they are not taken care properly. They say, "Government is introducing different schemes for our benefits, and we are ready to cooperate with the government too."

VI. CONCLUSION

The study reveals that the people of Malasa have cheerful outlook towards the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. It also tells the level of participation of people and the different activities conducted by them. The attitude of people is changed regarding the cleanliness and its importance due to the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan. On the other hand, there is a need of having a look on the working system of that specific department which have been assigned by this task.

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